

Polarographic Study of the Composition and Stability Constant of Citrate Complex of Mn(II)

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POLAROGRAPHIC reduction of Mn(II) in various aqueous and non-aqueous non-complexing media has been studied by a number of workers¹⁻⁵. Gaur et al.^{6,7} have undertaken a polarographic study of formate, sulphate and salicylate complexes of Mn(II). However, a polarographic study of the composition and stability constant of citrate complex is lacking. With this aim in view, it was thought worthwhile to undertake this study.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R., B.D.H. or E.Merck G.R. grade. Stock solution of Mn(II) was prepared by dissolving MnCl₂ in conductivity water and its concentration was kept at 1.0x10⁻³M. Potassium citrate solution was used as the source of citrate ions. KNO₃ was used to maintain constant ionic strength ($\mu=1.0$).

A manual polarograph (Toshniwal, CLO2) in conjunction with Toshniwal polyflex galvanometer (PL 50) was used to obtain current-potential curves. All the measurements were made at 25±0.1°. Triton X-100 (0.002%) was used as a maximum suppressor. Purified hydrogen was passed through the solution for removing dissolved oxygen. The d.m.e., used in conjunction with S.C.E., had the following characteristics :

$$h_{corr.} = 37.61 \text{ cm}$$

$$m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 3.016 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2} \text{ (in } 0.1 \text{ M KNO}_3 \text{, open circuit).}$$

Results and Discussion

Mn(II) gives a single diffusion controlled reduction wave at different concentrations of the citrate ions. The $E_{1/2}$ values are shifted to more negative potentials as the concentration of the ligand is increased thereby showing the complex formation (vide table 1). The reduction is quasi-reversible⁸⁻¹⁰. The values of $E_{1/2}^r$ at different concentrations of the ligand have been obtained (vide table 1) by Gellings' method¹¹. The plot of $E_{1/2}^r$ vs $\log C_x$ is a straight line (Fig. 1) indicating the formation of a single complex. The value of the co-ordination number 'j' comes out to be 2 and thus the composition of the complex is $[\text{Mn}(\text{citr.})_2]^{4-}$. The value of the stability constant (β) obtained by Lingane's method¹² comes out to be 5.2×10^5 .

TABLE 1—Mn(II)-CITRATE SYSTEM, $\mu=1.0$

[Pot. citrate] M	$-E_{1/2}^r$ V (S.C.E.)	$-E_{1/2}^r$ V (S.C.E.)	Slope V
0.000	1.515	1.510	0.0421
0.010	1.536	1.530	0.0431
0.020	1.568	1.562	0.0440
0.030	1.579	1.570	0.0450
0.040	1.590	1.580	0.0451
0.050	1.596	1.586	0.0462
0.060	1.599	1.592	0.0460
0.070	1.606	1.598	0.0452
0.080	1.612	1.605	0.0440

$j=2, \beta=5.20 \times 10^5$

Fig. 1. Plots of $E_{1/2}^r$ vs. $\log C_x$ (—○—) and $[(E_{1/2}^r)_c - (E_{1/2}^r)_s]$ vs. $\log C_x$ for Mn(II)-citrate system (—△—).

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